

SUPPORT

FACTSHEET

DELIVERABLE 2.1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK TO ASSESS THE SOCIOECOSYSTEM IN WHICH FARMERS HAVE TO OPERATE, AND HOW THIS AFFECTS THE USE OF IPM

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CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK TO ASSESS THE SOCIOECOSYSTEM IN WHICH FARMERS HAVE TO OPERATE, AND HOW THIS AFFECTS THE USE OF IPM

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SUMMARY

This brief is based on the publication [Towards sustainable crop protection in agriculture: A framework for research and policy.](#)

CONTEXT: European countries aim to reduce pesticide risks, but achieving this depends on widespread adoption of sustainable practices. How best to support farmers in this transition remains an open question.

OBJECTIVE: The study aims to review and enhance understanding of farmer decision-making and policy options to support the transition to sustainable crop protection, with a focus on European agriculture.

METHODS: The study develops a framework by reviewing the literature and integrating agronomic and economic perspectives. It focuses on three areas: indicators for measuring adoption, behavioural factors influencing farmer decisions, and methods for assessing adoption and related policies.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION: The study identifies four key findings: sustainable crop protection involves bundled practices often overlooked in policy; adoption should be measured by impact, not just uptake; behavioural factors are crucial but under-researched; and current policy tools fail to capture these complexities. These insights inform more effective policy design.

SIGNIFICANCE: This analysis informs policies aimed at reducing pesticide risks, identifies key research gaps, and provides frameworks to enhance future studies and policymaking in sustainable crop protection.

A FRAMEWORK FOR RESEARCH AND POLICY

The framework presented in the study outlines four interconnected categories that shape farmers' adoption of sustainable crop protection practices: (1) technical and economic characteristics of the practices, (2) market environment, (3) policy environment, and (4) farmer-specific behavioural factors. These categories interact in complex ways to influence decision-making and adoption dynamics. For example, the **cost-effectiveness**, **technical feasibility**, and potential yield impacts of sustainable practices affect their relative advantage over conventional methods. **Market conditions** - such as input prices, consumer demand, and retailer standards - can either support or hinder adoption, especially when sustainable products command price premiums or face consumer resistance. **Policy instruments**, including pesticide regulations, financial incentives, and support for alternatives, also play a critical role by shaping the economic and regulatory landscape in which farmers operate. Finally, **behavioural factors** such as risk tolerance, time preferences, and social networks significantly affect how farmers perceive and respond to both market signals and policy interventions.

INTERCONNECTED FACTORS AND THE ROLE OF CONTEXT IN ADOPTION

Importantly, these categories do not operate in isolation; for instance, behavioural responses can be shaped by available information (from policies or market actors), and adoption incentives depend on both policy design and technical feasibility. The framework highlights that adoption is highly context-specific, influenced by local agronomic, institutional, and economic conditions. It also emphasizes that sustainable crop protection strategies are often more complex and knowledge-intensive, requiring greater learning and support, which underscores the need for targeted extension services and capacity-building.

KEY HIGHLIGHTS

This study identifies critical factors influencing the adoption of sustainable crop protection and offers important insights to guide effective policy development and evaluation.

- **Sustainable crop protection is essential** to achieve national and international pesticide risk reduction targets.
- **Farmer behaviour and decision-making** play a critical role in the adoption of sustainable practices, offering valuable insights for more effective policy design.
- **Policy evaluation must go beyond adoption rates** and focus on measurable impacts, particularly reductions in pesticide risk.
- **Behavioural drivers are central but overlooked**—addressing these gaps can enhance the effectiveness of interventions.
- **This research supports evidence-based policymaking** aimed at accelerating progress toward safer, more sustainable agricultural systems.

STEPWISE APPROACH TO UNDERSTANDING AND SUPPORTING IPM ADOPTION

Step 1 established a joint framework to assess farmer behaviour and identify key opportunities and barriers to integrated pest management (IPM) adoption (this deliverable). Building on this foundation, **Step 2** is currently underway and involves comprehensive quantitative and qualitative analyses. This includes in-depth interviews with farmers and stakeholders across all 25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs), a large-scale survey accompanied by econometric analysis, choice experiments with a subset of the surveyed farmers, and additional data collection from farms contributing to the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). These diverse data sources aim to capture the complexity of farmer decision-making within varied socio-ecological contexts. Finally, **Step 3** will synthesize the quantitative and qualitative findings to provide a holistic understanding of IPM adoption dynamics and inform policy recommendations.

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In case you want to see other relevant deliverables regarding the SUPPORT project, click [here](#).

